

Comparison of rice hybridization methods

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The Bangkhen Rice Experiment Station has made crosses for the Thai breeding program for years, but the pace of rice hybridization has increased markedly since the introduction of high yielding varieties. Along with a dramatic increase in the number of crosses, there has been a shift in the methods of emasculation, from hot air to scissors, and, more recently, to vacuum emasculator. Since the merits of each procedure have not been closely examined, it seems appropriate to assess the three methods.

Six hundred florets of the Thai variety

Percent seed set when florets were emasculated and pollinated by different methods. Bangkhen Rice Experiment Station, Thailand.

Emasculation method	Av. seed set (%)			
	Pollen only		Pollen plus anther	
	One pollination	Two pollinations	One pollination	Two pollinations
Hot air	30	38	26	44
Scissors	18	44	58	66
Vacuum	40	52	50	64

Chi square = 102**

RD1 were used as female parents and IR34 was used as the pollinator. Data were recorded on the time required by each of the three emasculation methods, the percentage of seed set when plants were emasculated by each method, and the percentage of seed set resulting from different pollination techniques.

Seed set was higher with the vacuum

method than with either hot air or scissors. It was also higher when plants were pollinated twice on two successive days than when pollinated once. Adding a mature anther to the floret gave a higher seed set than dusting with pollen (see table). The conclusion is that the newer hybridization methods not only are faster but result in higher seed set. ~~W~~

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Agronomic characteristics

The term "intermediate-statured rice varieties" not a misnomer

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In monsoon Asia, where rice growth depends on rain, tall varieties are better adapted than semidwarfs. Domesticated tall varieties are attractive because of their ability to withstand medium-deep water, their vigorous early growth, and their leaf canopy that suppresses lush weed growth. In Kerala, farmers want tall rices so they can feed its lengthy straw to cattle. However, tall varieties lodge when heavily fertilized, significantly reducing yields. Thus, there has been a keen desire to combine desirable characteristics of tall varieties with high yielding ability and a new type of architecture: intermediate plant height.

Although intermediate-statured selections are available, their yielding ability has not been comparable with that of semidwarfs. Rice breeders have lately been selecting intermediate-statured plants and studying their yield potential.

Entries with that plant type from the International Rice Yield Nursery

Ranges in plant height and yields of entries tested at Pattambi, India.

		Plant ht (cm)					
60-70		70-80		80-90		90-100	
Cultivar	Yield (t/ha)	Cultivar	Yield (t/ha)	Cultivar	Yield (t/ha)	Cultivar	Yield (t/ha)
IET 2775	2.9	P881-19-22-12	2.7	BR 4	4.2	BR 51-46-5	5.1
IR8	3.4	IET 1785	3.9	IR2058	5.1	BR 51-74-6	4.0
IR26	2.3	IET 2080	3.4	IR2863	4.0	BR 52-87-1	4.5
		IET 2300	3.4	BG 374-1	4.7	P 901-22-11-2	4.4
		IET 2815	3.3	BG 374-2	4.0	B 44-b-50	3.7
		IET 4094	3.1	BG 375-1	4.6	B 541b-Kn	4.1
		IET 2911	3.7			B 542-b-pn-68	4.1
		IR2070-423-2-5-6	3.7			IR2823-399	4.8
		IR2071-596-5-6-3	3.1			C 168	3.9
		BG 96-3	4.1			WP 153	4.8
		IR2588-19-1-2-2	4.5				
		Taichung Sen Yu	4.2				
		Jaya	3.4				
Mean yield	2.9		3.6		4.4		4.4

(medium duration) were tested in replicated trials at the Rice Research Station, Pattambi. The check variety was Jaya, the most popular local semidwarf. Yields were categorized by plant height.

Taller rice cultivars yielded more than

semidwarfs (see table). Among the intermediate-height cultures, IR2058-78-1-3-2-3 and BR 51-46-5 yielded highest, 5.1 t/ha. The growth duration of the two varieties from seeding to harvest was 125 days. ~~W~~